

The Way of Former Heaven (Xiantiandao 先天道)

also known as “Qinglianjiao 青蓮教”

By Nikolas Broy, Leipzig University

Entry tags: Chinese Buddhist Traditions, Millenarianism, Confucian (rujia 儒家) Traditions, Min, Daoist Traditions, Syncretic Religions, Religious Group, Southeast Asian Religions, Chinese Buddhism, Buddhist Traditions, Language, Classical-Middle-Modern Sinitic, Self-Cultivation, Sino-Tibetan, Chinese Religion, Chinese Folk Religions, Sinitic, Chinese Buddhist Traditions

Xiantiandao 先天道, the “Way of Former Heaven,” is the common designation of a network of Chinese popular sects that share similar symbols, beliefs, and practices and from which many later Chinese redemptive societies, such as Yiguandao 一貫道 (“The Way of Pervading Unity”) and Tongshanshe 同善社 (“The Fellowship of Goodness”) emerged. In addition, Xiantiandao is a significant influence on the Vietnamese new religious movement Cao Dai (Đạo Cao Đài) that emerged from Sino-Vietnamese sectarian groups in 1920s French-colonial Saigon. While claiming descent from a genealogy of enlightened masters that goes back to the dawn of Chinese civilization, Xiantiandao emerged as a distinct religious group in eighteenth-century Jiangxi Province in southeastern China. In this early period, practitioners and outsiders seem to have referred to the sect and its teachings by various names, including Xiantiandao and Qinglianjiao 青蓮教 (“Green Lotus Sect”), a term that appears in nineteenth-century government surveillance material. Having appealed to traveling merchants and labor migrants in the nineteenth century, Xiantiandao quickly spread throughout southern and southwestern China and, from the 1860s onward, also to Chinese communities in Southeast Asia, especially in Thailand and what is now Singapore and Malaysia. Like many other nonofficial sects, Xiantiandao was subject to state persecution and vilification as an “evil sect” (xiejiao 邪教)—a deprecatory label employed by government officials and cultural elites to criminalize nonofficial religious groups that is still used today in public and political discourses in the People’s Republic of China (PRC). Accordingly, Xiantiandao was banned and persecuted by consecutive Chinese regimes, including the PRC. Thus, although almost entirely eradicated on the Chinese mainland since the early 1950s when it was considered a “counterrevolutionary sect” (fandong huidaomen 反動會道門), the sect still retained a considerable presence among overseas Chinese in Southeast Asia. In fact, state persecution has fueled Xiantiandao’s translocal spread in many ways. For instance, many practitioners were forced underground following a large-scale crackdown in southwestern China in the 1840s. With many leaders apprehended and executed and forced to act clandestinely, Xiantiandao branched into various subsects and local networks, many of which later evolved into independent sectarian groups. The well-known redemptive societies Tongshanshe and Yiguandao, but also others such as Guigendao 歸根道 (“The Way of Returning to the Origin”) split off from Xiantiandao during this period of instability in the second half of the nineteenth century. Similar to many other Chinese sects, Xiantiandao’s teachings are often described as “syncretic.” This characterization highlights its peculiar synthesis of established symbols and beliefs—most notably the so-called “Three Teachings” (sanjiao 三教) of Confucianism, Buddhism, and Daoism—and millenarian beliefs centering on the supramundane creator deity Wusheng Laomu 無生老母 (“Eternal Venerable Mother”) and her salvationist mission to rescue humankind from the impending apocalypse. Stressing individual moral self-cultivation as a means to restore one’s inherent original nature (a Buddhist concept), Xiantiandao practitioners seek to repatriate to Laomu’s “original homeland” (guxiang 故鄉) from which the early humans were exiled many eons ago. The sect’s teachings are immersed in a narrative of decline and moral corruption, according to which humankind is doomed to be annihilated in the final cosmic apocalypse, and only by following Laomu’s teachings will humans be able to restore their inherent

true selves and return to her eternal paradise. Like in many earlier popular sects during the Qing period and many later ones, including Yiguandao and Tongshanshe, this narrative is embedded in a cycle of three consecutive cosmic periods. Even though the final period, which is called baiyang 白陽 (“White Sun”), represents the beginning of the world’s end, it also marks the period during which the universal truth is being made available to all of humankind, whereas in earlier cosmic periods, only selected people had access to it. Accordingly, the baiyang period represents a time of high urgency to spread the teachings and help more people avoid the apocalypse. Besides highlighting how Confucian-oriented social values are instrumental in actualizing one’s true self, vegetarianism is crucial in Xiantiandao teachings. Drawing on Buddhist, Daoist, and Confucian notions of meat abstention and fasting, it serves many purposes, from ritual purification to ethical concerns and cleaning up karmic bonds of one’s past existences. In addition, many Xiantiandao rituals, individual and communal, are conceptualized in Daoist-inspired terms, most notably neidan 內丹 (“internal alchemy”). Adopting the trope of laboratory alchemy to conceptualize meditative practices, neidan practitioners typically seek to invert the natural course of life by refining subtle substances within the human body to nurture an immortal embryo that will withstand the decay and death of the physical body. Finally, as far as we know, Xiantiandao is the earliest Chinese sectarian group to have adopted spirit-writing (fuluan 扶鸞, “yielding the phoenix,” or fuji 扶乩, “yielding the planchette”) as a means of communicating with deities, Buddhas, bodhisattvas, and deceased leaders. While it was already a widespread practice in many different religious contexts, it was only in the 1820s to 1840s that spirit-writing gained currency in Xiantiandao. It became an essential means of religious text production and a source of legitimacy, especially regarding leadership and organization. In contrast to Buddhist and Daoist clerics, Xiantiandao sectarians consider themselves lay practitioners, meaning that most live ordinary lives and maintain families. The sect is organized according to a hierarchy of eight ranks, but the exact number may vary depending on which subsect, region, and period one looks at. This system channels access to the sect’s teachings and practices, whereby higher-level (“esoteric”) teachings are only available to accomplished practitioners. The rank-holders at the top of the hierarchy are also responsible for the overall organization and translocal proselytization. In many subsects, the highest four ranks are only available to men. Yet, researchers found that many practitioners and even entire communities are female, especially in Southeast Asia. Thus, during most of the twentieth century, Xiantiandao “vegetarian halls” (zhaitang 齋堂) in Thailand, Singapore, and Malaysia served as safe havens for unmarried women who sought to evade male-dominated lives and for widows. In traditional Chinese societies, Confucian values of obedience and female subordination strongly compelled girls and women to marry and give birth to children. Accordingly, seeking refuge in a Xiantiandao temple and living a chaste religious life was a rare opportunity to evade male domination. Because of the PRC’s strict religious policy and anti-sectarian agenda, Xiantiandao has almost disappeared from the Chinese mainland. Even though some communities survived in Taiwan and Southeast Asia and continued to thrive well into the twentieth century, ideological pressure from mainstream Buddhist groups led to a large-scale “Buddhisization” of Xiantiandao communities. Accordingly, many sites were converted into Buddhist monasteries and temples, and many sectarian practitioners formally became Buddhist monastics.

Date Range: 1734 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Nineteenth-Century southern China

Region tags: Asia, Late Imperial China, Sichuan 四川, East Asia, China, Jiangxi, Guizhou Province, Hunan Province, Hubei Province, China

Xiantiandao during the Qing Dynasty, ca. 1850s

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Topley, Marjorie. "The Great Way of Former Heaven: A Group of Chinese Secret Religious Sects." *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 26 (1963): 362–92.
- Source 2: Show Ying Ruo 蘇芸若. "Chinese Buddhist Vegetarian Halls (Zhaitang) In Southeast Asia: Their Origins and Historical Implications." NSC Working Paper, no. 28 (2018): 1–51.
- Source 3: Ngai Ting-Ming 危丁明. *Shumin de yongheng: Xiantiandao ji qi zai Gang Ao ji Dongnanya diqu de fazhan 庶民的永恆: 先天道及其在港澳及東南亞地區的發展*. Taipei: Boyang wenhua, 2015.
- Source 1: Lin Wanchuan 林萬傳. *Xiantian dadao xitong yanjiu 先天大道系統研究*. Tainan: Tianju shuju, 1986.
- Source 2: Jammes, Jérémy, and David A. Palmer. "Occulting the Dao: Daoist Inner Alchemy, French Spiritism, and Vietnamese Colonial Modernity in Caodai Translingual Practice." *The Journal of Asian Studies* 77, no. 2 (2018): 405–28.
- Source 3: Jammes, Jérémy, and David A. Palmer. "The Bible of the Great Cycle of Esotericism: From the Xiantiandao Tradition to a Cao Đai Scripture in Colonial Vietnam." In *Text and Context in the Modern History of Chinese Religions: Redemptive Societies and Their Sacred Texts*. Edited by Philip Clart, David Ownby and Chien-ch'uan Wang, 258–308. Leiden: Brill, 2020.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://jacinasack.wordpress.com/2015/10/25/keepers-of-our-faith-chua-khor-tai/>
- Source 1 Description: "Keepers of our Faith: Chuah Khor Tai," blog entry, October 25, 2015

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.taolibrary.com/>
- Source 1 Description: Collection of html and PDF scans of various Chinese and Taiwanese popular religious texts, including Xiantiandao.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: In recent decades, there is considerable competition in Southeast Asia and Taiwan between Xiantiandao practitioners and monastic Buddhists.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: Proselytization is strongly encouraged for all members. However, because of Xiantiandao's quantitative and qualitative decline in Taiwan and Southeast Asia during the past decades, many communities do not actively reach out to recruit new members.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Notes: Yet, there is a concept of divine retribution, according to which apostates will be punished by divine intervention.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

Notes: In the Xiantiandao hierarchy, holders of the rank shidi 十地 are responsible for overseeing regional affairs. They rank just below the supreme patriarch. The term literally means "ten places," but it is also a Buddhist technical term, translating the Sanskrit concept "daśabhūmi," which refers to the ten stages of religious cultivation.

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: This is the supreme patriarch (zu 祖 or zushi 祖師).

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

Notes: Under specific circumstances, such as during the government crackdown of Xiantiandao during the 1840s, local and regional leaders convened in the city of Hanyang 漢陽 in Hubei Province, which is part of the modern city of Wuhan 武漢, to discuss the future organization of the sect.

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 8

Notes: Because Xiantiandao produced a highly diverse network of religious groups in the nineteenth century, the exact number of ranks may differ. One of the more

elaborate and well-attested hierarchies includes the following ranks: 1) zushi 祖師 (patriarch) 2) shidi 十地 ("ten places," Skt. daśabhūmi) 3) dinghang 頂航 (supreme navigator) 4) bao'en 保恩 ("preserver of grace") 5) yin'en 引恩 ("guider of grace") 6) zheng'en 證恩 ("certifier of grace") 7) tian'en 天恩 ("heavenly grace") 8) zhongsheng 眾生 ("sentient being," a Buddhist term)

Reference: Topley, Marjorie. "The Great Way of Former Heaven. A Group of Chinese Secret Religious Sects". *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 26 (1963): 362-92.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– Yes

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– Yes

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

Notes: Yet, in post-WWII Taiwan, Xiantiandao leaders seem to have been selected by a council of leaders.

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Besides using various Buddhist, Daoist, and Confucian texts, Xiantiandao has a voluminous library of their own sectarian writings, including religious scriptures, printed rules and regulations, patriarchal genealogies, and texts received from the gods through spirit-writing (fuluan 扶鸞 or fuji 扶乩).

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Only religious public space

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Patriarchs, deities, Buddhas, and bodhisattvas are represented in human shape.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Notes: Unlike most other deities, Buddhas, and bodhisattvas in Chinese religions, the supreme extramundane creator Wusheng Laomu 無生老母 ("Eternal Venerable Mother") is not represented visually. Instead, her presence is represented through an oil lamp on the main altar. Being called the "Mother lamp" (laomudeng 老母燈) or "limitlessness lamp" (wujideng 無極燈), it symbolizes Laomu's unfathomable brightness and infinity. Therefore, the lamp also must stay lit all the time.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– I don't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– No

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

Notes: Laomu's paradise is sometimes described as the "heaven beyond heaven" (tianshangtian 天外天).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: Laomu's paradise, the "original home" (guxiang 故鄉 or jiaxiang 家鄉) is located outside of the ephemeral world we live in. Unlike "our" world, it is eternal and free from suffering.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme deity is Wusheng Laomu 無生老母 ("Eternal Venerable Mother"). Even though rendered in female terms, she is conceptualized as transcending conventional binaries. She is the sole creator of the cosmos and conceptualized as the "mother" of humankind who is considered her "children."

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: extramundane
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample

region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Especially through "spirit-writing" (fuluan 扶鸞 or fuji 扶乩). Through this means, many scriptures and texts have been revealed.
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– I don't know

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Yes

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
- ↳ Through divination processes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
- ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Yes
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes
Notes: Supernatural beings, such as dragons.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes
Notes: Demons and other nonhuman supernatural beings.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
– Yes

Notes: Supreme leaders, usually called "patriarchs" (zu 祖 or zushi 祖師), are recognized as incarnations of Buddhist, Daoist, or Confucian deities.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:
– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:
– Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:
 - No
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:
 - No
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - No

Notes: Usually, only beings not physically present communicate with the living in dreams. But because mixed beings, such as the Patriarchs (who are considered incarnations of Buddhist, Daoist, and Confucian higher gods), are physically present, they communicate with other people just as "regular" people would.

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Notes: Usually, only beings not physically present communicate with the living during spirit possessions. However, because mixed beings, such as the Patriarchs (who are considered incarnations of Buddhist, Daoist, and Confucian higher gods), are physically present, they communicate with other people just as "regular" people would.

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Notes: Usually, only beings not physically present communicate with the living through divination. However, because mixed beings, such as the Patriarchs (who are considered incarnations of Buddhist, Daoist, and Confucian higher gods), are physically present, they communicate with other people just as "regular" people would.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: Xiantiandao practitioners are expected to follow a vegetarian diet.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: For instance, meat is not allowed inside the temples.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Adultery:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Incest:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other sexual practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done only by high god:
 - No
 - ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No

- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - No

- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness[]:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In some Xiantiandao communities in the nineteenth century, rumors were spread about the imminent arrival of the Buddha of the future age, who is Maitreya Buddha. Sometimes, specific dates were mentioned, sometimes not. In rare cases, living people were identified as Maitreya Buddha's incarnation. Besides these historical instances, however, contemporary Xiantiandao practitioners do not seem to believe in the imminent arrival of Maitreya.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: Maitreya Buddha, the supreme leader in the last of the three cosmic periods, will lead those who have received the Xiantiandao teachings to restore their original natures and return to Laomu's paradise.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:
 - No
- ↳ Divine judgment event:
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world:
 - No
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Establishment of a new political system:
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of a new religious system:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:
 - No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Xiantiandao especially cherishes Confucian-oriented social moral values, such as filial piety (xiao 孝), ritual propriety, righteousness, loyalty, integrity, but also more general values, including industriousness, cleanliness, frugality, and temperance.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ What is the nature of this distinction:
 - Strongly present and highlighted

- ↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:
 - Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– Only one gender

– All individuals (any time period)

Notes: Some rules and regulations especially pertain to women. These include the “three obediences and four virtues” (sancong side 三從四德). According to this set of rules, women are not considered autonomous agents but only in relation to men they are expected to obey, i.e., their fathers, husbands, and sons.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):
– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– No

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Yet many committed practitioners, especially women, choose to live at temples known as "vegetarian halls" (zhaitang 齋堂). Often, these practitioners maintain full sexual abstinence and they do not marry.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Vegetarianism is compulsory for full membership. Contrary to Western forms of vegetarianism, Xiantiandao rules (like other Chinese forms of fasting and vegetarianism) also require practitioners to abstain from consuming alcoholic beverages and the "five pungent plants" (wuxin 五辛 or wuhun 五葷), which belong to the Allium genus, such as garlic, onions, and leek. This approach to fasting is shared by conventional Buddhists and some strands of Daoism, as well as Confucians (who, in premodern China, were required to fast before and during ritual events).

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Meat, alcoholic beverages, and the "five pungent plants" (wuxin 五辛 or wuhun 五葷), which belong to the Allium genus, such as garlic, onions, and leek, are not to be consumed.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

Notes: Donating one's property or wealth for spreading the Dao is very much encouraged.

↳ To out-groups:

– Yes

Notes: Charity is strongly encouraged, albeit not mandatory.

↳ Destroyed:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Practitioners are strongly encouraged to devote as much time as possible for moral self-cultivation, during rituals, but also to realize moral values in everyday life.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Besides formally accepting the pañcaśīla (five precepts) during initiation, Xiantiandao teachings stress that Confucian-oriented moral values are crucial for individual self-cultivation. The first are derived from Buddhism and constitute the single most important set of moral values for Buddhist lay practitioners and include prohibitions of killing, stealing, sexual misconduct, lying, and consuming intoxicants (such as alcoholic beverages). Furthermore, Confucian-oriented values are essential elements of the practitioners' daily lives. These include filial piety (xiao 孝), loyalty, obedience, ritual propriety, righteousness, and integrity. Furthermore, more general values, such as industriousness, cleanliness, frugality, and temperance, are cherished as well.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: Because proselytization is strongly encouraged, practitioners obviously need to maintain relationships with non-members. Yet, they also tend to favor interaction with fellow members.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 5

Notes: Small rites daily at morning, noon, and evening.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: Practitioners refer to co-religionists as “friends of the Way” (daoyou 道友).

Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: Xiantiandao emerged during the mid to late Qing-period of late imperial China and it thrived in various later sociopolitical settings, including the Republic of China (1912-1949), Taiwan (under Qing rule until 1895, under Imperial Japanese rule from 1895 to 1945, and as part of the Republic of China since 1945), and various southeast Asian countries, especially Thailand (a kingdom), Malaysia, and Singapore (former British colonies).

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: Especially in Southeast Asia, Xiantiandao "vegetarian halls" (zhaitang 齋堂) provide safe spaces and shelter for women and elderly female practitioners, in particular. In Hong Kong, Xiantiandao practitioners operate a retirement home called "Sin Tin Toa Home for the Aged" (Xiantiandao anlaoyuan 先天道安老院)

Reference: Topley, Marjorie. "Chinese Women's Vegetarian Houses in Singapore". *Journal of the Malayan Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society* 27 (1954): 51-67.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Xiantiandao is organized according to a hierarchy of eight ranks. These ranks do not merely correspond with access to higher teachings but also to organizational duties and responsibilities.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: Yet, during the turbulent period of the 1930s and 40s, during the Imperial Japanese aggression during WWII and the subsequent Chinese civil war between the Kuomintang (KMT) and the Chinese Communist Party (CCP), some local chapters seem to have been involved in organizing local militias for self-defense.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: Yet, during the turbulent period of the 1930s and 40s, during the Imperial Japanese aggression during WWII and the subsequent Chinese civil war between the Kuomintang (KMT) and the Chinese Communist Party (CCP), some local chapters seem to have been involved in organizing local militias for self-defense.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: Yet, rituals and observances are held on an annual basis according to the traditional Chinese lunisolar calendar.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: Some communities are known to have cultivated crops on their own, but this seems to have been an exception rather than the rule.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Way of Former Heaven (Xiantiandao 先天道), Topley, Marjorie. "The Great Way of Former Heaven. A Group of Chinese Secret Religious Sects". *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 26 (1963): 362–92.

Reference: The Way of Former Heaven (Xiantiandao 先天道), Lin 林, Wanchuan 萬傳. *Xiantian Dadao Xitong Yanjiu 先天大道系統研究*. Tainan: Tianju shuju, 1986.

Reference: The Way of Former Heaven (Xiantiandao 先天道), Jammes, Jérémy, and David A. Palmer. "Occulting the Dao. Daoist Inner Alchemy, French Spiritism, and Vietnamese Colonial Modernity in Caodai Translingual Practice". *The Journal of Asian Studies* 77, no. 2 (2018): 405–28. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021911817001425>.

Reference: The Way of Former Heaven (Xiantiandao 先天道), Jammes, Jérémy, and David A. Palmer. "The Bible of the Great Cycle of Esotericism. From the Xiantiandao Tradition to a Cao Đai Scripture in Colonial Vietnam". In *Text and Context in the Modern History of Chinese Religions. Redemptive Societies and Their Sacred Texts*. Leiden: Brill, 2020.

Reference: The Way of Former Heaven (Xiantiandao 先天道), Ngai 危, Ting-ming 丁明. *Shumin De Yongheng. Xiantiandao Ji Qi Zai Gang Ao Ji Dongnanya Diqu De Fazhan 庶民的永恆: 先天道及其在港澳及東南亞地區的發展*. Taipei: Boyang wenhua, 2015.

Reference: The Way of Former Heaven (Xiantiandao 先天道), Show 蘇, Ying Ruo 芸若. "Chinese Buddhist Vegetarian Halls (zhaitang) in Southeast Asia. Their Origins and Historical Implications". NSC Working Paper, 2018.

Reference: The Way of Former Heaven (Xiantiandao 先天道), Show 蘇, Ying Ruo 芸若. "The Blooming of the Azure Lotus in the South Seas. A Preliminary Investigation of Chinese Indigenous Scriptures in Buddhist Vegetarian Halls of Southeast Asia". *Journal of Chinese Religions* 48, no. 2 (2020): 233-84.

Reference: The Way of Former Heaven (Xiantiandao 先天道), Takeuchi 武内, Fusaji 房司. "Shindai Seirenkō No Kyūsai Shisō. En Mugi No Shosetsu O Chūshin Ni 清代青蓮教の救済思想：袁無欺の所説を中心に". *Chūgoku - Shakai to Bunka 中国：社会と文化*, no. 7 (1992): 53-68.

Reference: The Way of Former Heaven (Xiantiandao 先天道), Takeuchi 武内, Fusaji 房司. "Shinmatsu Shūkyō Kessha to Minshū Undō. Seirenkō Ryū Gijun Ha O Chūshin Ni 清末宗教結社と民衆運動—青蓮教劉儀順派を中心に". In *Chūgoku Minshū-shi E No Shiza - Kanagawa Daigaku Chūgokugo Gakka Sōsetsu Jūshūnen Kinen Ronshū 中国民衆史への視座—神奈川県中国語学科創設十周年記念論集*. Tokyo: Tōhō shoten, 1998.

Reference: The Way of Former Heaven (Xiantiandao 先天道), Takeuchi 武内, Fusaji 房司. "Sentendō Kara Kaodaikyō E 先天道からカオダイ教へ". In *Sensō Saigai to Kindai Higashi-ajia No Minshu Shūkyō 戦争・災害と近代東アジアの民衆宗教*. Tōkyō: Yūshisha 有志舎, 2014.

Reference: The Way of Former Heaven (Xiantiandao 先天道), Yau, Chi-on. "The Xiantiandao and Publishing in the Guangzhou-hong Kong Area from the Late Qing to the 1930s. The Case of the Morality Book Publisher Wenzaizi". In *Religious Publishing and Print Culture in Modern China, 1800-2012*. Berlin: de Gruyter, 2015.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Yes, Topley, Marjorie. "Chinese Women's Vegetarian Houses in Singapore". *Journal of the Malayan Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society* 27 (1954): 51-67.

Reference: Number of levels [numeric value]: 8, Topley, Marjorie. "The Great Way of Former Heaven. A Group of Chinese Secret Religious Sects". *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 26 (1963): 362-92.